

Minor oral surgery under anticoagulant therapy: A review of the literature

Wendy del Pilar Marca Sinchi *, Luz Carmen Paqui Abrigo and Od. esp. Mario Esteban Calderón Calle

Faculty of Dentistry, University of Cuenca, Cuenca, Ecuador.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 18(03), 944–952

Publication history: Received on 07 May 2023; revised on 14 June 2023; accepted on 16 June 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.18.3.1164>

Abstract

Objectives: This literature review seeks to know the management, as well as the limitations, indications, hemostatic measures and the risk to which compromised patients are exposed either by modifying the treatment or decreasing the dose prior to surgery treatment, as well as to establish the management of patients under therapy; before, during and after surgery.

Materials and methods: a literature review was carried out during the period September - December 2022. The sources used were the PubMed, ScienceDirect and Medline databases. The search terms were: (Warfarin) AND (Oral surgery), (Anticoagulation bridge) AND (Anticoagulant) AND (Dental extraction) AND (dentistry). Results: a total of 6281 articles were identified from the three databases used: pubmed, sciencedirect and medline. After applying the exclusion criteria, 3557 articles were eliminated, leaving a total of 2724 for reading and eligibility, resulting in 56 articles, 11 duplicate articles were excluded, leaving 45 articles for analysis and elaboration of the literature. Conclusions: compromised patients under treatment with direct oral anticoagulants (DOAC) or vitamin K antagonists (VKA) present a risk of intraoperative and postoperative bleeding, where VKA presents a higher risk compared to DOAC; it is recommended not to suspend the administration of anticoagulants either before or after surgery. Hemostasis can be controlled using different hemostatic measures.

Key words: Oral Surgery; Anticoagulation Bridge; Warfarin; Dentistry; Dental extraction.

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular disease is a pathology that is part of the chronic non-communicable diseases, it is one of the main causes of mortality and morbidity worldwide, the treatment used depends on the important risk factors which are expressed in a unique way in high, intermediate and low risk factors. Treatment can range from lifestyle changes to the administration of antithrombotics, the intensity of which depends on the size of the absolute risk. (1-3)

Due to the increased frequency of cardiovascular diseases, the number of patients on long-term anticoagulant therapy continues to increase worldwide. The therapeutic management of such underlying diseases is an internal medicine problem. However, with the increasing incidence of these diseases, anticoagulation therapy remains a primary problem in both high and low complexity oral surgery. (4,5)

Patients on anticoagulation therapy who require dental treatments or other minor oral surgery interventions often find their management challenging and clinically significant due to the risk of bleeding complications during the dental surgical procedure. (6,7)

Minor surgical procedures are actions of the daily clinical practice of the dentist, therefore a correct management of the patient compromised or not is essential, especially in those of the latter group due to the high risk of bleeding during

* Corresponding author: Wendy del Pilar Marca Sinchi

the procedure, among the most performed practices are: Exodontia with alveolar preservation technique, Surgical exodontia of third molars, Labial frenilectomies, Lingual frenilectomies, Dentoalveolar traumas, Apicoectomies, etc.... (8)

The drugs mostly used are vitamin K antagonists (VKA) such as warfarin and acenocoumarol, direct thrombin inhibitors, direct factor Xa inhibitors, known as direct acting oral anticoagulants (DOAC) such as apixaban, edoxaban, rivaroxaban and dabigatran indicated for the prevention of thromboembolism due to its more predictable action. Dabigatran appeared as an option to warfarin for anticoagulation in the treatment of atrial fibrillation (AF). The risk associated with bleeding due to its use has been evidenced in several trials, but no large study has examined in detail the risk of bleeding in the process of tooth extraction and other dental procedures involving bleeding. (9-13)

VKAs inhibit vitamin K-dependent coagulation factors (II, VII, IX, X), these are characterized by a slow onset of action, their effect takes 5 to 7 days, the international normalized ratio (INR) determines the intensity of the anticoagulant effect of VKAs so that the INR in a healthy patient is 0.9 to 1.6, this range depends on each pathology, thus in patients with mechanical valve prostheses and in pulmonary thromboembolism with antiphospholipid syndrome the INR is 2.5 to 3.5; meanwhile, most patients with atrial fibrillation, ischemic stroke, acute myocardial infarction and embologenic valvulopathies the INR is 2. (14, 40)

DOACs are new anticoagulant agents that specifically disrupt a single factor in the coagulation system, either activated factor X or thrombin. (15)

They feature "antithrombotic agents" that give them a more predictable effect in blood compared to (VKAs) (16).

This literature review seeks to know the management as well as limitations, indications, hemostatic measures and the risk to which compromised patients are exposed either by modifying or suspending the dose of treatment prior to surgery as well as to establish the management of patients under therapy before, during and after oral surgery.

2. Materials and Methods

Under the question what is the risk to which patients under anticoagulant therapy are subjected during dental extractions and what is the protocol to follow? A literature review was conducted during the period September - December 2022. The sources used were the PudMed, ScienceDirect and Medline databases. The search terms were: Warfarin) AND (Oral surgery), (Anticoagulation bridge) AND (Anticoagulant) AND (Dental extraction) AND (dentistry).

Controlled clinical trials, observational, practice guidelines, risk factor studies, research case reports, meta-analyses, literature reviews, research articles, systematic reviews, comparative, prospective, cross-sectional studies published in the last 5 years, with no language limit, were taken into account. Articles that are animal studies, books, commentaries, article responses, and that are not part of the last 5 years of publication were excluded.

Reviewed articles were collected, stored, and organized using Microsoft Excel 2016.

Flowchart

Figure 1 Flow diagram of the selection of articles for the literature review: A total of 6281 articles were identified from the three databases used: pubmed, sciencedirect and medline. After applying the exclusion criteria, 3557 articles were eliminated, leaving a total of 2724 for reading and eligibility, resulting in 56 articles, 11 duplicate articles were excluded, leaving 45 articles for analysis and elaboration of the literature.

3. Results

Over time, different dental surgery protocols have been generated for patients with anticoagulants, and these are modified in relation to the anticoagulant therapy they receive. There are two families of drugs used: vitamin K antagonists and direct oral anticoagulants. It has now been demonstrated that there is a greater risk for the patient when anticoagulant therapy is interrupted because it can produce thromboembolism and "rebound hypercoagulation", compared to post-extraction bleeding when continuing with anticoagulants.

3.1. Theoretical framework

3.1.1. Risk

The management of ASA II patients under anticoagulant therapy should be treated with caution taking the necessary measures and having adequate safety to provide efficient care to the compromised patient, therefore, it is necessary to know the risks to which patients are subjected.

The risk of slowing healing and increasing hemostasis during third molar extraction, specifically in the extraction of the lower third molar in those patients treated with warfarin tends to be notably higher, however, risk factors significantly influence during the surgical procedure, among them are an increased prothrombin time value (PT-INR), preoperative administration of prophylactic antibiotics, elevated serum creatinine levels and postoperative bleeding after extraction in patients under VKA. (17-19)

Current studies are moving towards the prescription of direct oral anticoagulants, which have fewer interactions and better perioperative management. (20)

Systolic blood pressure control is also important during tooth extraction to avoid complications in patients taking warfarin and in hypertensive patients not taking warfarin. The highest systolic blood pressure (SBP) values were

observed in patients receiving warfarin before administration of local anesthetics (highest SBP = 0.9415 mm Hg) and in hypertensive patients not taking warfarin (highest SBP = 1.0027 mm Hg). (21, 41)

In elderly patients regardless of the type of anticoagulant, the dental extraction procedure may generate postoperative bleeding problems after dental extraction due to the influence of other medical problems, caution is accurate even more when they are being administered with rivaroxaban. (22, 42)

3.2. Risk in case of multiple extractions

If patients on anticoagulants are scheduled to undergo multiple tooth extractions or their HAS-BLED score (scale for calculating the risk of bleeding in patients with atrial fibrillation receiving oral anticoagulation, based on risk factors)²². If the scale is above 3 points in the case of warfarin, patients are informed about the risk of bleeding after the extraction, risk-benefit should be considered before the operation and hemostasis should be carefully performed, and patients should be instructed to bite down precisely on the gauze for longer than normal. (23)

3.3. Protocols in patients undergoing vitamin K antagonist (VKA) therapy during minor or major oral surgery procedures.

- continue VKAs with no change in administration
- discontinued days before with heparin
- discontinued days before surgery

3.3.1. Continue VKAs with no change in their administration.

VKA treatment should be continued for all surgical procedures if the INR is in the therapeutic range (warfarin INR<4.0) the American College of Chest Physicians recommends an INR of 2.0-3.0 for most cardiac conditions therefore discontinuation of antiplatelet therapy prior to dental extractions is not necessary, hemostasis can be achieved by applying local measures. (24)

3.3.2. Stopped before with heparin, stopped before surgery.

Anticoagulation therapy with warfarin, whether continued, suspended or joined a few days before surgery with heparin therapy, is not indicated due to the complexity of managing vitamin K antagonists, their interaction with various medications and foods, and their persistent need for monitoring of effectiveness and their blood concentration, in other words may increase the risk of other complications, such as thromboembolic diseases (25, 43)

3.3.3. Reducing the dose days before surgery.

Factors such as diet, concomitant use of other medications and other comorbidities may alter the activity of anticoagulants for such reason reducing the dose before surgery presents risks of thromboembolic complications that outweigh the risks of bleeding events. (26)

3.4. Protocols in patients undergoing DOAC during minor or major oral surgery procedures

Maintain unchanged direct oral anticoagulant therapy and apply local hemostatic measures.

Following minor oral surgery such as tooth extractions, the risk of postoperative bleeding is slightly lower in patients receiving DOAC without interruption of DOAC administration both preoperatively and postoperatively compared to patients receiving VKA, therefore, it is NOT necessary to adjust the dose of DOAC prior to tooth extractions.(27,28)

Discontinue DOACs one day before or one day after surgical treatment.

Compared to VKAs, DOACs have different pharmacokinetics, their plasma concentrations vary from 3-4 hours and their half-lives vary from 10-17h, allowing an immediate onset and loss of their anticoagulant effects, which has led to consider the suspension of their administration prior to surgery compared to warfarin, which has a prolonged half-life and a subtherapeutic dose that could leave the patient in a prothrombotic state. (29, 44)

3.5. Protocol for dental extractions in anticoagulated patients.

The management of the compromised patient should be widely known due to the number of patients that require dental extractions and this being a daily practice of the dentist, their knowledge and management should be sufficiently clear to eradicate any type of complication during the intervention.

Table 1 Protocol for dental extraction in anticoagulated patients. (45)

DOAC		AVK	
Extraction of 1 to 3 pieces and minor procedures	Extraction of ≥ 4	Extraction of 1 to 3 pieces and minor procedures	Extraction of ≥ 4
normal vital signs Laboratory exams normal blood count INR < 4.0	Request advice from the oral and maxillofacial surgery department and/or contact the patient's doctor to determine risk factors	normal vital signs Laboratory exams normal blood count INR < 4.0 normal pt normal PTT	Request advice from the oral and maxillofacial surgery department and/or contact the patient's doctor to determine risk factors
Anticoagulant therapy is maintained- extraction in 1-3 pieces		Anticoagulant therapy is maintained at intervals of 4 to 6 h- extraction in 1-3 pieces	
Antibiotic coverage if necessary, surgical approach extractions in 1st 3 pieces DOAC/ AVK			
light bleeding		moderate bleeding	severe bleeding
Gauze compression 30 min Chew the gauze soaked with a fibrinolytic agent		Application of a topical hemostatic with a gelatin sponge (gelfoam or oxidized cellulose tape, along with single suture)	Systemic therapy or hospitalization
postoperative medication		postoperative medication	
4.8% mouth rinse use 4 times a day for 2 minutes - follow-up			

3.6. Hemostatic measures

Among the hemostatic agents used to control bleeding, the literature has highlighted oxidized cellulose, resorbable gelatin sponges, collagen sponges, fibrin glue, cyanoacrylate glue, platelet-rich plasma gel, calcium alginate and topical thrombin. Local interventions, such as sutures, sealants, adhesives, ligature clips, vasoconstrictor agents, or combination of these measures have also been used to control bleeding. (30, 31)

Hemostatic interventions also include antifibrinolytic agents, such as tranexamic acid (TXA) which helps promote safe hemostasis at the surgical site to improve intraoperative visibility and postoperative hemostasis. The importance of antifibrinolytic mouth rinses in the prevention of post-extraction bleeding has been observed in several studies. They are used to mitigate bleeding in surgical procedures because they stabilize and inhibit the breakdown of blood clots. (32,33)

In all studies reviewed by Ockerman et al (2019) : mentions that during minor oral surgery, employing the technique of gauze pressure as a primary hemostatic measure, in combination or not with sutures in conjunction with other hemostatic measures allows greater control of bleeding in patients under dual and single antiplatelet therapy, hemostatic measures included: absorbable collagen sponges, gelatin or gelfoam gauze impregnated with Tranexamic Acid as a primary hemostatic method and gauze pressure and re(suturing) as a secondary hemostatic measure in case bleeding occurred. All studies confirmed that local hemostatic measures were adequate to stop bleeding however the risk of perioperative bleeding in minor oral surgery is higher in patients receiving dual antiplatelet therapy than in those receiving single antiplatelet therapy. (34, 35,36)

3.7. Platelet-rich fibrin (PRF)

It is made up of three key parameters that distinguish it from platelet-rich plasma.

Activated platelets and growth factors: they are introduced into the fibrin matrix in the natural polymerization process

Leukocytes and their cytokines: provide anti-infective action and assist in immune regulation in the healing process . Natural density and organization without anticoagulants and gelling agents.

The fibrin matrix promotes angiogenesis, facilitating access to the injured site, playing an important role in residual healing.

However, according to the study by Edson et al. (2021) From a total of 130 patients to whom platelet-rich fibrin was applied after tooth extraction it was shown that the use of FRP in extraction wounds did not reduce the risk of bleeding after extraction in anti-coagulated patients ($P = 0.330$; $I2 = 99\%$). did not reduce pain ($P = 0.470$; $I2 = 96\%$) or the risk of postoperative alveolitis ($P = 0.4300$; $I2 = 38\%$). (37)

Local hemostatic agents such as TXA and feracrylum stop bleeding without having systemic action and without the need to alter the anticoagulant regimen. Feracrylum has the added advantage of a single application, formation of a mechanical barrier and an additional antimicrobial effect. These agents should be incorporated into the protocol for managing patients on oral anticoagulants. (38, 39)

4. Conclusions

Patients who are under treatment with DOAC or VKA and who undergo minor surgical interventions are at risk of intraoperative and postoperative bleeding regardless of the range in which they are, however in this literature review it was corroborated that patients under VKA have a slightly higher level of risk compared to patients under DOAC regardless of whether the surgical procedure is of lesser or greater complexity.

Almost all the articles reviewed recommend not to suspend the administration of anticoagulants either before or during the surgical procedure, and that hemostasis can be controlled according to the level of bleeding by means of hemostatic measures, including topical hemostatic application, especially TXA zhaguicon, a gelatin sponge, gelfoam or oxidized cellulose tape, together with individual suture, compression with gauze for 30 min soaked with an antifibrinolytic agent and in case of severe bleeding use systemic therapy or hospitalization, however the latter must be previously communicated to the oral surgery department.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We would like to express our most sincere gratitude to Dr. Mario Calderón for his professional help and patience in the preparation of this work.

Likewise, I, Wendy Marca, want to thank my siblings Wilmer, Marina, Carolina and my parents Manuel and Pilar, especially my mother Pilar for always supporting me in spite of everything and my grandmother Lucinda who is in heaven for being my guardian angel throughout this journey, this goal has been achieved by the support of my entire family.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors did not declare any potential conflict of interest with respect to the research, authorship and/or publication of this article.

References

- [1] Vega Abascal Jorge, Guimar Mosqueda Mayra, Vega Abascal Luis. Cardiovascular risk, a useful tool for the prevention of cardiovascular diseases. Rev Cubana Med Gen Integr [Internet] 2011 March [cited 2023 May 10]; 27(1): 91-97. Available at: http://scielo.sld.cu/scielo.php?pid=S0864-21252011000100010&script=sci_arttext&tlng=en
- [2] Zemplenyi K, Dillon JK. Oral and maxillofacial surgery and hematologic diseases. In: Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery for the Medically Compromised Patient. Cham: Springer International Publishing; 2022. p. 99–108.
- [3] Souza BCR de. Dental management of patients on anticoagulant therapy: literature review. 2022 [cited 2023 Jun 12]; Available at: <http://200.150.122.211/jsui/handle/23102004/394>
- [4] Buchbender M, Schlee N, Kesting MR, Grimm J, Fehlhofer J, Rau A. A prospective comparative study to assess the risk of postoperative bleeding after dental surgery while taking direct oral anticoagulant, antiplatelet agent, or

- vitamin antagonist medication K. BMC Oral Health [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2023 Jun 9];21(1):504. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12903-021-01868-7>
- [5] Brennan Y, Gu Y, Schifter M, Crowther H, Falavero EJ, Curnow J. Dental extractions on direct oral anticoagulants versus warfarin: the DENTST study. *Res Pract Thromb Haemost* [Internet]. 2020;4(2):278–84. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/rth2.12307>
- [6] Johansson K, Götrick B, Holst J, Tranæus S, Naimi-Akbar A. Impact of direct oral anticoagulants on bleeding tendency and postoperative complications in oral surgery: a systematic review of controlled studies. *Oral Surgery Oral Med Oral Patol Oral Radiol* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2023 Jun 9];135(3):333–46. Available at: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/36100547/>
- [7] Queiroz SIML, Silvestre VD, Soares RM, Campos GBP, Germano AR, da Silva JSP. Tranexamic acid as a method of local hemostasis after dental extraction in patients on warfarin: a randomized controlled clinical study. *Clin Oral Research* [Internet]. 2018;22(6):2281–9. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00784-017-2327-4>
- [8] Lee JS, Kim MK, Kang SH. Effect of discontinuation of warfarin on the incidence of postoperative bleeding in dental extraction. *J Korean Assoc Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2020 [cited 2023 Jun 9];46(4):228–34. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5125/jkaoms.2020.46.4.228>
- [9] Manfredini M, Poli PP, Creminelli L, Porro A, Maiorana C, Beretta M. Comparative bleeding risk of anticoagulant therapy with vitamin K antagonists (VKAs) and with non-vitamin K antagonists in patients undergoing dental surgery. *J Clin Med* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2023 Jun 9];10(23):5526. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/jcm10235526>
- [10] Andrade MVS, Andrade LAP, Bispo AF, Freitas L de A, Andrade MQS, Feitosa GS, et al. Assessment of bleeding intensity in patients anticoagulated with warfarin or dabigatran undergoing dental procedures. *Arq Bras Cardiol* [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2023 Jun 9];111(3):394–9. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5935/abc.20180137>
- [11] Hua W, Huang Z, Huang Z. Bleeding outcomes after dental extraction in patients on direct-acting oral anticoagulants versus vitamin K antagonists: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Pharmacol* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2023 Jun 9];12:702057. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.3389/fphar.2021.702057>
- [12] Engelen ET, Schutgens REG, Mauser-Bunschoten EP, van Es RJJ, van Galen KPM. Antifibrinolytic therapy for preventing oral bleeding in people on anticoagulants undergoing minor oral surgery or dental extractions. *Cochrane Libr* [Internet]. 2018 [citado el 9 de junio de 2023];2018(7). Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/14651858.cd012293.pub2>
- [13] Bensi C, Belli S, Paradiso D, Lomurno G. Postoperative bleeding risk of direct oral anticoagulants after oral surgery procedures: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2018 [citado el 9 de junio de 2023];47(7):923–32. Disponible en: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29627150/>
- [14] Iwata E, Tachibana A, Kusumoto J, Takata N, Hasegawa T, Akashi M. Does prophylactic antibiotic administration for tooth extraction affect PT-INR in patients taking warfarin? *BMC Oral Health* [Internet]. 2020 [citado el 9 de junio de 2023];20(1):331. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s12903-020-01326-w>
- [15] Andrade NK, Motta RHL, Bergamaschi C de C, Oliveira LB, Guimarães CC, Araújo J de O, et al. Bleeding risk in patients using oral anticoagulants undergoing surgical procedures in dentistry: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Pharmacol* [Internet]. 2019 [citado el 9 de junio de 2023];10:866. Disponible en: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31447671/>
- [16] Manfredi M, Dave B, Percudani D, Christoforou J, Karasneh J, Diz Dios P, et al. World workshop on oral medicine VII: Direct anticoagulant agents management for invasive oral procedures: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Oral Dis* [Internet]. 2019 [citado el 9 de junio de 2023];25 Suppl 1(S1):157–73. Disponible en: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31140701/>
- [17] Ono S, Ishimaru M, Yokota I, Konishi T, Okada A, Ono Y, et al. Risk of post-extraction bleeding with direct oral anticoagulant compared with warfarin: Retrospective cohort study using large scale claims data in Japan. *Thromb Res* [Internet]. 2023;222:24–30. Disponible en:
- [18] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0049384822004844>
- [19] Lu S-Y, Lin L-H, Hsue S-S. Management of dental extractions in patients on warfarin and antiplatelet therapy. *J Formos Med Assoc* [Internet]. 2018;117(11):979–86. Disponible en:
- [20] <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0929664618305436>

- [21] Inokoshi M, Kubota K, Yamaga E, Ueda K, Minakuchi S. Postoperative bleeding after dental extraction among elderly patients under anticoagulant therapy. *Clin Oral Investig* [Internet]. 2021;25(4):2363–71. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00784-020-03559-z>
- [22] Yamada S-I, Hasegawa T, Soutome S, Yoshimura H, Miyakoshi M, Ueda N, et al. Prevalence of and risk factors for postoperative hemorrhage after lower third molar extraction on warfarin therapy: a multicenter retrospective study in Japan. *Odontology* [Internet]. 2020;108(3):462–9. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10266-019-00474-y>
- [23] Kubota K, Yamaga E, Ueda K, Inokoshi M, Minakuchi S. Comparison of cardiovascular response between patients on warfarin and hypertensive patients not on warfarin during dental extraction. *Clin Oral Investig* [Internet]. 2021;25(4):2141–50. Disponible en: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00784-020-03526-8>
- [24] Visakha Suresh, Muath Bishawi, Michael W. Manning, Jacob Schroeder, Mani Daneshmand, Management of Patients With Left Ventricular Assist Devices Requiring Tooth Extraction: Is Withholding Anticoagulation Appropriate?. 2017; 76(9). Available at: [https://www.joms.org/article/S0278-2391\(17\)31348-4/fulltext#secsectitle0070](https://www.joms.org/article/S0278-2391(17)31348-4/fulltext#secsectitle0070)
- [25] Sato K, Chikuda M, Miyamae Y, Kan M. Cardiopulmonary arrest with airway obstruction due to postoperative bleeding. *Case Rep Dent* [Internet]. 2021 [citado el 8 de enero de 2023];2021:8861061.
- [26] Cabbar F, Cabbar AT, Coşansu K, Çekirdekçi Eİ. Effects of direct oral anticoagulants on quality of life during perioperative management for dental extractions. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2019;77(5):904–11.
- [27] Foo M, See L, Lee J, Feng B, Kruger E. Current practices of Western Australian general dentists regarding management of patients on anticoagulant/antiplatelet therapy. *Aust Dent J* [Internet]. 2021;66(4):385–90.
- [28] Yoshikawa H, Yoshida M, Yasaka M, Yoshida H, Murasato Y, Fukunaga D, et al. Safety of tooth extraction in patients receiving direct oral anticoagulant treatment versus warfarin: a prospective observation study. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2019;48(8):1102–8. Disponible en: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S090150271930030X>
- [29] Andrade MVS, Andrade LAP, Bispo AF, Freitas LA, Andrade MQS, Feitosa GS, Feitosa-Filho GS. Evaluation of the Bleeding Intensity of Patients Anticoagulated with Warfarin or Dabigatran Undergoing Dental Procedures. *Arq Bras Cardiol*. 2018 Sep;111(3):394-399. doi: 10.5935/abc.20180137. Epub 2018 Aug 6. PMID: 30088558; PMCID: PMC6173350.
- [30] Douketis JD, Spyropoulos AC, Murad MH, Arcelus JI, Dager WE, Dunn AS, et al. Executive summary: Perioperative Management of Antithrombotic Therapy: An American College of Chest Physicians Clinical Practice Guideline. *Chest* [Internet]. 2022 [citado el 8 de enero de 2023];162(5):1127–39.
- [31]
- [32] Lababidi E, Breik O, Savage J, Engelbrecht H, Kumar R, Crossley CW. Assessing an oral surgery specific protocol for patients on direct oral anticoagulants: a retrospective controlled cohort study. *Int J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2018;47(7):940–6. Disponible en: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S090150271830095X>
- [33] Moreno-Drada JA, Abreu LG, Lino PA, Parreiras Martins MA, Pordeus IA, Nogueira Guimarães de Abreu MH. Efectividad de los hemostáticos locales para prevenir el sangrado en pacientes dentales con anticoagulación: una revisión sistemática y un metanálisis en red. *J Craneomaxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2021;49(7):570–83. Disponible en: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1010518221001232>
- [34] AlSheef M, Gray J, AlShammari A. Risk of postoperative bleeding following dental extractions in patients on antithrombotic treatment. *Saudi Dent J* [Internet]. 2021;33(7):511–7.
- [35] Baldoni M, Lauritano D. Bleeding control with calcium sulphate after oral surgery in anticoagulant therapy patients. *J Biol Regul Homeost Agents*. 2019;33(6 Suppl. 1):41-48. DENTAL SUPPLEMENT.
- [36] Ockerman A, Vanhaverbeke M, Miclotte I, Belmans A, Vanassche T, Politis C, et al. Ácido tranexámico para reducir el sangrado después de la extracción dental en pacientes tratados con anticoagulantes orales sin vitamina K: diseño y justificación del ensayo EXTRACT-NOAC. *Br J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2019 [citado el 12 de junio de 2023];57(10):1107–12. Disponible en: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31669068/>
- [37] Radhakrishna S, Shukla V, Shetty SK. ¿Es el apósito dental de quitosano mejor que la gasa de algodón para lograr la hemostasia en pacientes con antitrombóticos? *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2023;81(2):224–31. Disponible en: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0278239122009764>

- [38] Ambrogio RI, Levine MH. Tranexamic acid as a hemostatic adjunct in dentistry. *Compend Contin Educ Dent* [Internet]. 2018 [citado el 12 de junio de 2023];39(6):392–401. Disponible en: <https://pesquisa.bvsalud.org/bvsecuador/resource/en/mdl-29847965>
- [39] Yamunaque Vire JM. manejo de la extracción dental en pacientes sometidos a terapia anticoagulante: una revisión de la literatura. *odontol act rev cient* [internet]. 2021 [citado el 12 de junio de 2023];6(2):27–36. disponible en: <https://oactiva.ucacue.edu.ec/index.php/oactiva/article/view/566>
- [40] Filho ELC, Franco JMPL, Ribeiro TR, Silva PG de B, Costa FWG. Does platelet-rich fibrin prevent hemorrhagic complications after dental extractions in patients using oral anticoagulant therapy? *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2021 [citado el 12 de junio de 2023];79(11):2215–26. Disponible en: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34343502/>
- [41] Rai S, Rattan V. Efficacy of Feracrylum as Topical Hemostatic Agent in Therapeutically Anticoagulated Patients Undergoing Dental Extraction: A Comparative Study. *J Maxillofac Oral Surg*. 2019 Dec;18(4):579-583. doi: 10.1007/s12663-018-1156-6. Epub 2018 Sep 27. PMID: 31624440; PMCID: PMC6795659.
- [42] Hiroshi I, Natsuko SY, Yutaka I, Masayori S, Hiroyuki N, Hirohisa I. Frequency of hemorrhage after tooth extraction in patients treated with a direct oral anticoagulant: A multicenter cross-sectional study. *PLoS One* [Internet]. 2022;17(4):e0266011.
- [43] Zou L, Hua L. Risk of bleeding with dental implant surgery in patients on anticoagulant or antiplatelet drugs: a systematic review and meta-analysis [published online ahead of print, 2022 Jun 28]. *Acta Odontol Scand*. 2022;1-7. doi:10.1080/00016357.2022.2085324
- [44] Nazar J. C, Cárdenas C. A, Coloma D. R, Contreras C. JI, Molina I, Miranda H. P, et al. Manejo perioperatorio de pacientes con tratamiento anticoagulante crónico. *Rev Chil Cir* [Internet]. 2017 [citado el 24 de enero de 2023];70(1):84–91.
- [45] Tabrizi R, Khaheshi I, Hoseinzadeh A, Rezvanpour B, Shafie S. ¿Los medicamentos antiplaquetarios aumentan el riesgo de sangrado después de la cirugía de implante dental? Un estudio de casos y cruces. *J Oral Maxillofac Surg* [Internet]. 2018;76(10):2092–6.
- [46] Escalante Otárola W, Castro Núñez G, Geraldo Vaz L, Kuga MC. Fibrina rica en plaquetas (FRP): Una alternativa terapéutica en odontología. *Rev Estomatol Hered* [Internet]. 2016 [citado el 12 de junio de 2023];26(3):173. Disponible en: http://www.scielo.org.pe/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1019-43552016000300009
- [47] Dds JF, Dds PC, Ouanounou A. Dental management of patients undergoing antithrombotic therapy [Internet]. *Com.co*. [citado el 12 de junio de 2023]. Disponible en: https://odontologos.com.co/assets/doc/news/2021-06-17_013550anti_trombo.pdf
- [48] Yamunaqué JM, Reyes FM, Guillén PF. Manejo de la extracción dental en pacientes sometidos a terapia anticoagulante [revisión de la literatura]. *Revista OACTIVA UC Cuenca*. Vol. 6, No. 2, pp. 1-10, Mayo-Agosto, 2021.